

A Hybrid Deep Learning Model CNN-GRU for Crop Yield Prediction Under Climate Impacts: A Case Study of Rice Yield Prediction in India

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Abstract:

Rice is one of the most important crops grown throughout India and has a significant impact on the socioeconomic status of the country. The Indian Summer Monsoon (ISM) provides a crucial water supply that supports rice production. However, climate change has led to erratic weather patterns that exacerbate the intensity of climate variables. Given the relationship between climate and rice production, it is important to understand and predict rice yields to strengthen the resilience of the socioeconomic sector. Recent improvements in deep learning models show greater predictive capabilities in extracting spatial or temporal features. This study aims to develop a hybrid deep learning-based model for rice yield prediction in India by integrating CNNs with GRU and using climate projection data from CMIP6 and AgMIP crop models. The model shows good prediction accuracy but tends to slightly overestimate yields, especially in northeast India. The predictions indicate a decline in rice yields, with significant losses expected under the SSP585 scenario.

Keywords: Crop prediction, Climate impacts, Artificial Intelligence, Indian Summer Monsoon.

Introduction:

In 2020, India was the second-largest rice producer, accounting for 24% of the world's rice production (FAO Faostat, 2022). The agricultural sector employs more than 40% of the population in two prominent growing seasons (Rabi and Kharif). Moreover, it is inherently sensitive to climate change. Wheeler *et al.*, (2000) predict a steep decrease in crop productivity when atmospheric temperatures exceed critical physiological thresholds of crops, with Knox *et al.*, (2012) suggesting a severe impact on India due to greater crop losses and less availability of food per capita. Cooper *et al.*, (2019) suggest that changing precipitation may lead to more hunger and stunting in child development. Higher temperatures correlate to low-calorie availability, childhood malnutrition, and higher food prices (Ringler *et al.*, 2010), demanding the investigation of climate drivers influencing the region.

Past studies indicate a negative correlation between Niño 3.4 Sea Surface Temperature Anomaly (SSTA) and the Indian Summer Monsoon Rainfall (ISMR), with El Niño causing lower than average

rainfall and La Niña generally resulting in excess rainfall in the Indian Subcontinent (Goswami and An, 2023). Notably, out of 13 drought years in India since 1950, 11 coincide with El Niño years, although not all El Niño events result in droughts, as seen in 2006 and 1997-98. The relationship has weakened over time.

Additionally, ENSO is a significant trigger for Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) events, while IOD can enhance ENSO's intensity (Shukla and Paolino, 1983). Their interactions affect ISM rainfall, with positive IOD events sometimes leading to normal rainfall during strong El-Niño years, while negative IOD can diminish La Niña's positive effects (Karumuri *et al.*, 2001). These climate patterns have substantial socioeconomic impacts, influencing agricultural productivity and food security.

Thus, the subject holds vital importance on both regional and global scales. Therefore, the development of projects aimed at generating climate projections, such as the Agricultural Model Intercomparison and Improvement Project (AgMIP) and Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6), in addition to the development of artificial intelligence models, is fundamental. They are responsible for generating data that can guide management and decision-making at the local level, as well as adaptation measures to mitigate the impacts of a changing climate on countries' food and economic security. Thereby, although AgMIP hasn't provided predictions of crop yield in SSPs scenarios yet, various studies have made use of AgMIP for assessing historical crop yield data. For instance, Tumbo *et al.*, (2020) used AgMIP and five GCMs from CMIP5 and concluded that the risk of loss of farm income in the study area is around 50-60% of the farms. Similarly, Heinicke *et al.*, (2022) evaluated GCMs in all AgMIP-ISIMIP2a models and detected that the yield was reduced due to droughts and heatwaves.

Several studies highlight the efficacy of machine learning in agriculture, especially in crop yield prediction and climate change impact assessment. Crane-Droesch (2018) demonstrated that a deep neural network outperformed traditional statistical methods in predicting corn yields in the US Midwest. Paudel *et al.*, (2021) combined crop modelling with machine learning for yield forecasting in Europe.

Therefore, this study aims to develop a new deep learning model using a combination of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) layer for the prediction of rice crop yield using CMIP6 and AgMIP data in India.

2) Data and Methods

2.1) Data

In this work, we used the CMIP6 historical and climate projection data obtained through Pangeo (<https://storage.googleapis.com/cmip6/pangeo-cmip6.json>) for the models NorESM-MM (Bensten *et al.*, 2019) and MIROC6 (Shiogama *et al.*, 2019) under the SSP245 and SSP585 scenarios. The variables downloaded were monthly precipitation, surface temperature, relative humidity, Sea Surface Temperature (SST), and soil moisture data. This data was then averaged for each year. The gridded crop data were obtained from the models EPIC-Boku (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1404765>), LPJ-GUESS (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1408639>), LPJmL (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1403060>) and PEPIC (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1403209>). The observed precipitation and temperature data are obtained from the Indian Meteorological Department (https://www.imdpune.gov.in/cmpg/Griddata/Rainfall_25_NetCDF.html), Normalised difference vegetation index (NDVI) data are obtained from GIMMS (<https://zenodo.org/records/7441559>). The crop yield models EPIC-Boku, LPJ-GUES

LPJmL and PEPIC were used because only these models had predictions in the data spanning between 1901 to 2011. Furthermore, the Niño 3.4 SST anomalies were calculated for 1901 - 2011 using the reference period of (1850 - 1900). Similarly, the Dipole Mode Index (DMI) was calculated for the same period. Thereafter, the ensemble model mean of both input variables and rice crop yield data was calculated.

2.2) Methods

2.2.1 Regression analysis

In this section, we performed statistical relationship analysis, such as Pearson's correlation and pairplot, to uncover the relationship between the regional climate variables, remote climate indices (Enso and IOD), and rice yield in India.

2.2.2 Deep learning model

The first step was to normalise the data between 0 and 1. After that, the data were split 80% for training, 10% for validation, and 10% for testing randomly. The training was applied using a cross-validation technique.

After that, a convolutional neural network was developed with surface temperature, precipitation rate, relative humidity, and soil moisture as first input variables with four hidden layers with 32, 64, 128, and 128 filters with kernels (3, 3). Besides, the DMI and Niño3.4 indexes were also computed in an input layer with a GRU hidden layer with 32 units for capturing temporal patterns of the indexes. Subsequently, the information of spatial and temporal inputs is combined in a dense layer with 2014 neurons before the output layer. The real activation functions were used in all hidden layers.

Moreover, the loss function used was Mean Squared Error (MSE), and the error metric evaluated was the Mean Absolute Error (MAE). The best optimiser evaluated was Adam. The developed machine learning model was used to predict the rice crop yield over India for the CMIP6 SSP245 and SSP585 scenarios, and the results were analysed. In the case of scenario SSP245, the soil moisture variable wasn't available in the model, so we used soil moisture projection from SSP585 in SSP245.

3) Results

3.1 Statistical analysis

In Figure S2, we performed a Pearson's correlation analysis between anomalies of the variables with rice yield. The analysis reveals that rice yield is weakly correlated with relative humidity, soil moisture, and Niño 3.4 and very weakly correlated with precipitation and temperature. This indicates that precipitation affects rice yield indirectly through soil moisture and humidity. Additionally, while the DMI shows a strong positive correlation with precipitation, the lack of a clear correlation between ENSO and precipitation is unexpected. These findings may reflect model limitations, raising concerns about the adequacy of the rice yield model and CMIP6 climate models in capturing these relationships. The relationship can also be observed in the scattered pairplots in Figure S3, where the scattered plots lie along the regression line for strongly correlated variables and are very scattered for weakly correlated variable.

3.2 Model Evaluation

The model evaluation starts with the error metric analysis in training and validation (Figure 1). MSE reached values on the order of 0.0007 while MAE reached 1% using 30 epochs, which was considered a satisfactory result.

After this process, the split test data was used to evaluate the model's predictions. Thus, the climatic data and the time series of global oceanic indices were used as input data for the model, and its output was subsequently compared with the observed results of rice yield prediction. Finally, the percentage difference was calculated for each grid point between the predicted and observed data pixels (Figure 2).

In general, the model overestimated by a range between 1% to 3% in most parts of India except for the northeast, where it was overestimated by 3 to 6%.

3.3 Rice crop yield prediction

With good performance metrics, we now apply the model to predict future rice yield in India under the SSP245 and SSP585 emission scenarios. Figure S6 compares the projected rice yield S6a and the historical yield S6b and their differences. This analysis shows areas of high rice yield (blue) and low rice yield (red). The figure shows a significant rice yield loss under this emission scenario in the future, with these losses exacerbated under the SSP585 emission scenarios (Figure 3). In conclusion, if the Paris Agreement is not strictly followed, increasing emissions of CO₂ can exacerbate regional food insecurity in India by the end of the century.

The projected time series for rice yield in India using the CNN-GRU model developed in this work can be found in Figure 4. This figure shows a decline in rice yield under future warming, with the SSP585 scenario causing more losses compared to the SSP245 scenario.

4) Discussion and conclusion

Considering that multiple research investigations have proven machine learning works efficiently in predicting agricultural yields (Crane-Droesch et al., 2018; Paudel et al., 2021) a deep learning model was developed using a combination of CNN and GRU techniques to integrate spatial features of temperature, precipitation rate, relative humidity, and soil moisture over India with the temporal characteristics of the DMI and ENSO 3.4 ocean indices. The model achieved acceptable error metrics, with an MAE around 1% and percentage differences between predicted and observed values not exceeding 5% across India.

Although the model tended to overestimate rice crop yield in the analysed test data, the projections indicated a decline in rice crop yield under SSP 245 and 585 scenarios, like Heinicke *et al.*, (2022).

Besides, for future studies, it is fundamental to validate the AgMIP model's results with observation data because the predictions strictly depend on these model outputs. We acknowledge that this validation is missing in this study, and this would impact the results that we obtained. Also, it can include high-resolution datasets for future evaluation and improvement.

However, given these findings, a governance approach with a systemic vision that prioritises no-regret actions related to mitigation and adaptation is crucial, particularly to alleviate the social and economic impacts that a systemic decline in rice production could cause in India and globally due to the changing climate.

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Figure

Figure 4

Figure 1 - Training and validation loss over epochs; Figure 2 - Percentage Difference between predicted and observed values; Figure 3: Shows the differences between the mean of the model projection (from 2015 to 2100) and the historical SSP585 projection; 3a shows the model output for rice production under SSP 585; 3b shows the historical production; 3c shows the difference between the periods ; Figure 4 - Rice crop yield time series over India.

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